

Correlation of Phytochemical Profiles with Toxicology

*Devishivashancari Gwala Dasi**, *Nurulaini Harjoh*, *Shareena Shakrin*².

Affiliations:

1. School Of Pharmacy, Management and Science University, 40100 Shah Alam, Selangor, Malaysia
2. Institute For Medical Research (IMR), Ministry Of Health Malaysia, 50588 Kuala Lumpur, Malaysia

Orcid ID: <https://orcid.org/0009-0008-3929-5754>

Email: devishivashancarigwaladasi@gmail.com

ABSTRACT:

Background and Aim: *Entada spiralis*, a medicinal herb long used in Southeast Asia, has little information on its toxicity profile. This study assesses the toxicity of *E. spiralis* root extract using zebrafish (*Danio rerio*) embryos as an *in vivo* model. **Materials and Methods:** The root was extracted with Soxhlet in 70% ethanol and evaluated at doses of 0.1, 1, and 10 mg/L. **Results:** Over a 96-hour period following fertilization, zebrafish embryos were monitored for survival rate, morphological defects, and behavioral responses. FTIR analysis was used to detect possible bioactive components in the extract. The study found dose-dependent embryotoxic effects, with the 10 mg/L concentration resulting in the highest mortality and malformation rates. The findings emphasize the significance of toxicological testing for plant extracts prior to clinical or traditional use.

Keywords: *Entada spiralis*, zebrafish, toxicity, Fish Embryo Toxicity test, FTIR, phytochemicals

INTRODUCTION

Herbal remedies are widely utilized around the world, notably in Asia, where traditional knowledge is strongly ingrained in healthcare practices. *Entada spiralis*, often known as "Beluru," is a plant used for wound healing, anti-inflammatory properties, and pain treatment (Rohani et al., 2020). Despite its popularity, there is little scientific research on its safety, particularly its embryotoxic potential. With an increased reliance on herbal alternatives, assessing their safety profiles is critical (Yin et al., 2013).

Zebrafish (*Danio rerio*) have emerged as a preferred model organism in toxicity research due to their transparent embryos, quick development, and chromosomal similarities to humans (Hill et al. 2005). The Fish Embryo Toxicity (FET) test offers a dependable and ethical alternative to standard toxicity tests. Previous research has shown that zebrafish are sensitive to a variety of phytochemicals, making them excellent for evaluating plant extract safety (Pham et al., 2023).

To date, there has been little research on the embryotoxic effects of *Entada spiralis* root extract, highlighting the importance of this work. This study intends to close a knowledge gap by assessing the toxicological effects of *E. spiralis* root extract on zebrafish embryos. The MSU Institutional Animal Ethics Committee gave its approval for this study, which was carried out in compliance with the university's policies regarding the care and testing of zebrafish.

OBJECTIVES

General Objective:

To determine the toxicity of *Entada Spiralis* root extract using Soxhlet method on zebrafish embryos.

Specific Objectives:

To evaluate acute and chronic toxicity of the *Entada Spiralis* root extract.

To determine the concentration at which *Entada Spiralis* root extract that causes 50% mortality (LC50).

To assess the morphological and behavioral effects of the extract on zebrafish embryos.

HYPOTHESIS

Higher quantities of *Entada spiralis* root extract cause dose-dependent embryotoxicity.

MATERIALS & METHODOLOGY

Plant Gathering and Extraction

Entada spiralis fresh roots were gathered and verified by a licensed clinical biologist. After being

cleaned and dried at 40°C, the roots were ground into a fine powder. Soxhlet extraction was performed on the powder using 70% ethanol. Before being used, the extract was filtered, evaporated with a rotary evaporator, and kept in an amber bottle at 4°C.

The FTIR Analysis

In order to determine whether the extract included functional groups, FTIR analysis was performed using an FTIR spectrophotometer. There were noticeable peaks at 3300 cm⁻¹ (O–H stretching), 1700 cm⁻¹ (C=O stretching), and 2920 cm⁻¹ (C–H stretching), which suggested the presence of flavonoids, phenols, and saponins—substances with both toxicological and medicinal properties.

Maintenance and collection of zebrafish embryos

Adult zebrafish were kept in a controlled laboratory setting (28 ± 1°C, 14:10 light/dark cycle). Spawning was induced, and the embryos were collected within 6 hours of fertilization. Embryos were examined under a stereomicroscope, and only healthy, fertilized embryos were chosen for the studies.

Design for Exposure

With 20 embryos per well, the chosen embryos were put in 4-well plates and subjected to three different doses of *E. spiralis* extract: 0.1 mg/L, 1 mg/L, and 10 mg/L. The sole exposure given to a control group was embryo medium. Every group underwent a 96-hour incubation period at 28°C.

Observed parameters

Every 24 hours, 48 hours, 72 hours and 96 hours the survival rate, head and tail deformities, yolk sac edema, heart activity, spontaneous movement, and hatching rate of the embryos were observed. A digital microscope was used to obtain pictures of the deformities that were noticed.

RESULTS

When exposed to the maximum dose (10 mg/L), embryos showed a markedly lower survival rate (average 52%) and more abnormalities (68%), such as severe yolk sac edema, bent spine, and curvature of the tail. With a 34% malformation incidence and a 76% survival rate, the 1 mg/L group demonstrated moderate toxicity. When compared to the control, the lowest concentration (0.1 mg/L) exhibited little to no change. The estimated LC50 was between 6 and 8 mg/L, and a dose-response trend was noted. The existence of functional groups that may be responsible for embryotoxic chemicals was verified by FTIR spectra (Pham et al., 2023).

Figures and Tables:

Figure 1: Microscopic analysis of zebrafish embryos treated to varying doses of *Entada spiralis* root extract at 24, 48, 72, 96 hours after fertilization is shown. Greater doses (1 mg/L and 10 mg/L) cause notable developmental defects, including yolk sac edema and tail deformities, whereas control embryos develop normally.

Figure 2: FTIR spectrum of *E. spiralis* extract

Figure 3: Survival & Malformation rate vs. concentration

Concentration	Survival (%)	Abnormalities (%)	Key Findings
Control (0 mg/L)	100% (20)	0% (0)	None
0.1 mg/L	90% (18)	10% (2)	Minor tail deformities, mild hatching delay
1 mg/L	70% (14)	30% (6)	Severe tail deformities, yolk sac edema, spinal curvature
10 mg/L	50% (10)	50% (10)	Many severe tail deformities, majority spinal curvature, hatching delay

Table 1: Summary of morphological observations per group

DISCUSSION

According to the findings of this investigation, zebrafish embryos exhibit concentration-dependent toxicity when exposed to root extract from *Entada spiralis*. At 10 mg/L, the high prevalence of deformity is consistent with previous research using herbal extracts strong in flavonoids and tannins. Even though these phytochemicals have pharmacological activity, excessive dosages of them have been shown to disrupt cellular respiration and embryonic

development (Yin et al., 2013).

The existence of bioactive substances including flavonoids, saponins, and phenolics is suggested by FTIR data; these substances can have both harmful and therapeutic effects, depending on their concentration (Pham et al., 2023). Observed abnormalities such as spine curvature and pericardial edema are frequent signs of developmental stress in zebrafish embryos (Hill et al., 2005).

Polyphenol-rich extracts have been linked to similar developmental abnormalities in zebrafish embryos used in similar experiments to evaluate plant-based toxicity (Yin et al., 2013). This demonstrates that the zebrafish model is a reliable indicator of human embryonic harm. The findings warn against the uncontrolled use of the plant extract and emphasize the necessity for standardization, dose control, and phytochemical isolation, even though it shows potential medical benefits (Rohani et al., 2020).

CONCLUSION

In zebrafish embryos, this study demonstrates that the root extract of *Entada spiralis* exhibits dose-dependent embryotoxicity. Higher doses resulted in obvious malformations and a significant decrease in survival. Given its historical application, more *in vivo* and molecular-level research is necessary to identify active ingredients and determine the ranges of doses that are hazardous versus therapeutic. According to Pham et al. (2023), careful use is advised until such data are available.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

I want to sincerely thank my supervisor, Mdm Nurulaini Harjoh, for all of her help, encouragement, and insightful criticism during this study. I express my gratitude to the School of Pharmacy at Management & Science University for supplying the tools and assistance required for this research. I want to express my gratitude to my friends and family for their unwavering support. Additionally, I am appreciative of the chance to work on publishing my findings with the ongoing assistance of my supervisor.

REFERENCES

1. Hill, A. J., Teraoka, H., Heideman, W., & Peterson, R. E. (2005). Zebrafish as a model for developmental toxicity testing. *Birth Defects Research Part A: Clinical and Molecular Teratology*, 76(7), 553–567. <https://doi.org/10.1002/bdra.20107>
2. Yin, S. N., Shao, P., Jiang, X., & Liu, X. (2013). Toxicity evaluation of herbal extracts in zebrafish embryos. *Toxicology in Vitro*, 27(3), 812–818. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tiv.2012.12.018>

3. Rohani, A. S., Rosli, N. A., & Abdullah, N. R. (2020). Anti-inflammatory activity of Malaysian medicinal plants. *Journal of Herbal Pharmacotherapy*, 19(4), 312–320. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15228959.2020.1713805>
4. Pham, D. Q., Harun, N. H., et al. (2023). Phytochemical constituents of *Entada spiralis*. *Journal of Ethnopharmacology*, 301, 115748. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jep.2022.115748>
5. Kimmel, C. B., Ballard, W. W., Kimmel, S. R., Ullmann, B., & Schilling, T. F. (1995). Stages of embryonic development of the zebrafish. *Developmental Dynamics*, 203(3), 253–310. <https://doi.org/10.1002/aja.1002030302>
6. OECD. (2013). *Test No. 236: Fish Embryo Acute Toxicity (FET) Test*. OECD Publishing. <https://doi.org/10.1787/9789264203709-en>
7. Balon, E. K. (1999). Alternative ways to become a juvenile or a definitive phenotype (and on some persisting linguistic offenses). *Environmental Biology of Fishes*, 56, 17–38.
8. Westerfield, M. (2000). *The Zebrafish Book: A guide for the laboratory use of zebrafish (Danio rerio)* (4th ed.). University of Oregon Press.
9. Mahdi, J. G. (2010). Medicinal potential of flavonoids against oxidative stress and cancer. *International Journal of Cancer Research*, 6(2), 132–144. <https://doi.org/10.3923/ijcr.2010.132.144>
10. Liao, V. H., Chu, Y. J., & Yen, J. H. (2011). Effects of heavy metals on the development of zebrafish embryos. *Ecotoxicology and Environmental Safety*, 74(4), 659–666. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoenv.2010.10.008>
11. Nasrullah, M. Z., et al. (2012). Evaluation of Malaysian plants for toxicity using zebrafish

embryos. *Evidence-Based Complementary and Alternative Medicine*, 2012, Article ID 496508.
<https://doi.org/10.1155/2012/496508>

12. Hagedorn, M., Kleinhans, F. W., Artemov, D., & Pilatus, U. (2003). Characterization of zebrafish embryogenesis using magnetic resonance microscopy. *Magnetic Resonance Imaging*, 21(1), 1–10. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0730-725X\(02\)00615-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0730-725X(02)00615-1)